

AI4

eOSC

AI4EOSC Catalogue of Services

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable gathers the complete catalog of services that integrate the AI4EOSC platform. We provide a table-based view of the information of each service, grouping services by work packages. We end with a section describing how those services integrate with the broader EOSC ecosystem.

1. INTRODUCTION

OBJECTIVES

The AI4EOSC project aims to provide a set of advanced services specifically tailored to the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models and applications within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). To answer this challenge, the project has developed a platform comprising a catalog of services, whose architecture has been described in the previous deliverables [\[D3.2\]](#), [\[D3.3\]](#).

This deliverable describes the final state of the catalog of services² at the end of the project, as well as their integration with the broader EOSC ecosystem. The vision of the AI4EOSC project is to increase the service offer in the EU landscape by expanding the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem to support the effective utilization of state-of-the-art AI techniques by the research community. AI4EOSC strives also to provide an easy entry point for non-technological users, resulting in an effective usage of pan-European distributed e-Infrastructures.

In [Section 2](#), we provide the detailed list of AI4EOSC services, in a table-based format. In [Section 3](#) we detail the different components that comprise those services. And finally, in [Section 4](#), we explain how these services integrate with others from the EOSC ecosystem.

2. CATALOGUE OF SERVICES

In this section, we collect the compilation of services that are part of the AI4EOSC catalog. Service will be presented in a table-based format, providing service name, description, category, public URL, key features, and the list of service subcomponents (that are further described in [Section 3](#)).

Unless stated otherwise, all services share the following information:

² Where, following the standard IT definition [\[fitsm-vocabulary\]](#), we define a service as an asset that delivers an added value to the user. In our case, users are either end users (scientists) or platform operators. Services can be composed of one or more service components.

Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://status.ai4eosc.eu/
Documentation and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation is available in: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/ (for all components developed internally) How-tos and other more specific materials are also available: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/howtos/index.html https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/others/video-demos.html
SLA	SLA to be agreed with final users and offered generically on a best-effort basis. Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) and Platform Privacy Policy are available here: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/acceptable-use-policy/ https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/privacy-policy/
Contact Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contact details: https://ai4eosc.eu/contact/ User Support: https://helpdesk.services.ai4os.eu/ Support for software issues is managed through GitHub issues in the code repo.

Moreover, it is worth mentioning that, regarding the sustainability of the services presented in this section, we have elaborated an exploitation and sustainability plan that is presented in detail in Deliverable 2.4 [D2.4].

AI4EOSC PLATFORM

Service Name	AI4EOSC Platform
Service Description	The AI4EOSC platform provides an easy to use toolbox to develop artificial intelligence and machine learning models in the EOSC.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, AI/ML, Analytics
Public URL	https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive user and development environments. Federated and distributed model training, transparent e-Infrastructure access. Data annotation tools. Metadata for model lineage and provenance. Rich model metadata. FAIR assessment of ML models. EOSC repository and storage integration. Automated dataset synchronisation Automated deposit of developed models in Zenodo and other repositories

Service components	Authentication, Secrets Manager, Container Registry, Storage, Status, Dynamic DNS, Workload Management System, Inference Platform, Platform API, Platform Dashboard, Provenance Manager, Metadata Manager, CI/CD, Templates Hub
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AI4EOSC AI AS A SERVICE

Service Name	AI4EOSC AI as a Service
Service Description	A platform for serverless event-driven data-processing applications that allows the deployment of AI models as services on a cloud environment, providing an accessible and efficient means to perform inference.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, AI/ML, Analytics
Public URL	https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different methods of deploying services as serverless functions, short lived endpoints or on premises deployments. • Automated integration with AI4EOSC platform, with continuous delivery in place. • Integration with different storage systems.
Documentation and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation is available in: https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/ • Howtos and other more specific materials are also available: https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/training/
Service components	Inference Platform, Authentication

AI4COMPOSE

Service Name	AI4Compose
Service Description	AI4Compose is a software suite designed to integrate and orchestrate various AI models and machine learning techniques into organised workflows. It supports visual programming tools like Elyra and Node-RED, allowing users to create and manage AI inference pipelines through intuitive graphical interfaces. AI4Compose is integrated with OSCAR for executing inference tasks, facilitating the incorporation of AI models into data science workflows with precision and efficiency.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, AI/ML, Analytics

Public URL	Node-RED (FlowFuse): https://forge.flows.dev.ai4eosc.eu Elyra (integrated in EGI Notebooks): https://notebooks.egi.eu
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual composition of AI inference pipelines. • Integration with OSCAR to efficiently outsource AI model inference on distributed infrastructures. • Integration with EGI Notebooks. • Flexibility and scalability. • User-friendly interface.
Documentation	https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/pipelines/index.html
Service components	AI4Compose

AI4EOSC EXPERIMENT TRACKING

Service Name	AI4EOSC Experiment Tracking
Service Description	The AI4EOSC Experiment Tracking allows users to track AI/ML experiments from testing to staging and to production. In addition to the support for logging metrics, it also serves as a model registry.
Service Category	Compute, AI/ML, Analytics
Public URL	https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central place for users to store AI/ML experiments, runs, and models. • Self-registration AAI. • User-friendly handling of experiment and model permissions.
Documentation	https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/develop/mlflow.html
Service components	Experiment Tracking and Model Registry, Authentication, Secrets Manager

AI4EOSC DRIFT MONITORING

Service Name	AI4EOSC Drift Monitoring
Service Description	The AI4EOSC Drift Monitoring service allows users to monitor their production model for drift. Using our drift detection methods generate

	drift metrics that will be sent to the Driftwatch service for easy visualization.
Service Category	Compute, AI/ML, Analytics
Public URL	https://drift-watch.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python drift detection framework, supporting both concept drift with data drift. • Python client to log drift metrics. • Central server to collect and visualize the drift monitoring metrics with a friendly interface.
Documentation	https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/develop/drift-watch.html
Service components	Drift detection, Drift monitoring, Authentication

AI4EOSC TEMPLATES HUB

Service Name	AI4EOSC Templates Hub
Service Description	The AI4 Templates Hub allows developers and users to create software project repositories, following AI4EOSC best practices and recommendations. These templates provide an easier path to integrate a module in the AI4EOSC marketplace, as they include all the required metadata and other code assets needed. A user-friendly web interface to generate new repositories is provided.
Service Category	AI/ML, Analytics, Repositories
Public URL	https://templates.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different template flavours, focusing on different user needs (advanced, minimal, child-module) • Easier integration of user developed modules in the AI4OS marketplace. • Web interface and API for effortless generation of software projects
Documentation and Resources	https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/reference/cookiecutter-template.html
Contact Information	The AI4 Templates Hub is based on the more general Templates Hub service: https://templates.services.fedcloud.eu

Service Components	Templates Hub, Authentication
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AI4EOSC LLM

Service Name	AI4EOSC LLM
Service Description	The AI4EOSC LLM allows users to interact with a catalog of deployed Large Language Models, including both text-based and vision based models from several open-source AI providers (Mistral, Qwen). Through protected OpenAI-compatible APIs, users are able to integrate this service into their own components.
Service Category	AI/ML, GenAI
Public URL	https://llm.dev.ai4eosc.eu/
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Friendly UI to interact with LLM. • Catalog of different open-source LLMs. • Supports both text-based and vision-based workloads. • Open-AI compatible API to integrate with external services.
Documentation and Resources	https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/reference/llm.html
Service components	AI4EOSC LLM, Authentication

AI4EOSC PLATFORM ORCHESTRATION

Service Name	Platform Orchestration
Service Description	A set of microservices that allow access to distributed cloud compute and storage resources in a transparent and federated way.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, Cloud, Resource Management
Public URL	https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TOSCA-based deployment orchestration service on multiple IaaS. • Cloud-oriented federation service.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ready-to-deploy user-oriented services over cloud IaaS.
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it accessible after authentication.
Documentation and Resources	References: https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc
Support and SLA	Support is given for the federated resources and related activities available within the project. Support for the deployment of user-oriented services is given within the scope of the project.
Contact Information	Support and information can be provided by INFN via the Distributed Systems Unit mailing list: ds@cnaf.infn.it
Service components	PaaS Orchestration, Authentication

INFRASTRUCTURE MANAGER

Service Name	Infrastructure Manager
Service Description	Infrastructure Manager is an IaaS tool designed to manage the creation of virtual infrastructures by deploying and configuring virtual appliances on different cloud providers, making infrastructures cloud-agnostic. It simplifies the process by making the deployment and management of the infrastructures automatic.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, Cloud, Resource Management
Public URL	https://im.egi.eu
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automation of virtualized infrastructure deployment and configuration with software installation. • Support for multiple Cloud back-ends. • Multi-modal access (Web-based application for user-friendly interface, command-line application for advanced usage and REST API for easier integration).
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://status.ai4eosc.eu/
Documentation and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The official documentation can be found here: https://imdocs.readthedocs.io • Video tutorials with demos can be found in the YouTube IM reproduction list here: Infrastructure Manager - YouTube

Support and SLA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detail the support options available for the service and the Service Level Agreement (SLA) terms. • Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) and Platform Privacy Policy are available: https://im.eji.eu/im-dashboard/static/terms.html https://im.eji.eu/im-dashboard/static/privacy.html
Contact Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support tickets for the service can be sent through GGUS: https://ggus.eu/ assigned to the 'Infrastructure Manager' support unit. • Software issue tickets can be sent to the IM GitHub Issues: https://github.com/grycap/im/issues • Additional support can be provided via: products@grycap.upv.es
Service components	Infrastructure Manager

3. SERVICE COMPONENTS

In this section, we detail the individual service components that compose the different services introduced in the previous section.

Components are listed into four main categories, relating them to the work package where each one has been developed. The first category collects components that apply horizontally to the whole platform, like the authentication or the Docker registry, where container images are stored. The next three subsections contain the components developed by or directly related to WP4, WP5 and WP6, respectively.

For each component, we provide a summary sheet with this key information: name, brief description, key features, link to the code repository, main technologies involved, license and, if applicable, public endpoint where the production instance of the service is running. In addition we will provide a “developed” information, detailing on whether a given component has been developed “internally” (i.e. by one of the project members) or “externally” (i.e. the platform has deployed it with a custom configuration, but with no significant code modifications were made to it).

As a reference, we provide in **Figure 1** an overview of the overall AI4EOSC architecture. This serves as a guide when reading the next section, in order to locate the place of each individual component in the overall project architecture. For a more detailed description of the different components, please refer to deliverables D4.5 **[D4.5]** and D5.5 **[D5.5]**.

Figure 1: Overview of the AI4EOSC platform architecture.

3.1 - CROSS-PLATFORM COMPONENTS

The horizontal services of the platform are those that are used across many different work packages. These services include:

Authentication

Name	Authentication
Developed	Externally
Description	The AI4EOSC Authentication system is used across all the AI4EOSC stack to authorize users into the platform. To easily onboard external communities it allows the federation of external identity providers, like EGI Check-In or MyAccessID. By implementing a careful role mapping, we grant fine-grained user permissions into the platform based on the different user identities.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federation of multiple external AAI systems (e.g. EGI CheckIn, MyAccess ID). • Manage per-component access levels through fine-grained user roles. • Integrated with every component of the platform. • Customized to support additional user information, like API keys for services.

Code	https://github.com/keycloak/keycloak https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-api-keys
Technologies	Keycloak, OIDC
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://login.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/

Name	INDIGO IAM
Developed	Internally
Description	<p>The Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure service for the PaaS Orchestrator component layer - and related resource providers - is provided by the INDIGO Identity and Access Management Service (INDIGO-IAM) that leverages the OpenID Connect and OAuth2.0 protocols.</p> <p>INDIGO-IAM allows the federation of external identity providers, like eduGAIN, EGI Check-In or MyAccessID. By implementing a role mapping, fine-grained user permissions can be granted among the different federated resource providers.</p>
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OpenID connect provider based on the MitreID OpenID connect library. ● SCIM user provisioning and management APIs. ● SAML authentication support. ● OIDC authentication support. ● X.509 authentication support. ● OAuth token exchange support.
Code	https://github.com/indigo-iam/iam
Technologies	OIDC, OAuth2.0
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://aai.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/

Secrets manager

Name	Secrets manager
Developed	Externally
Description	The AI4EOSC Secrets manager is used to manage user sensitive data across the platform. Using the battle-tested Vault open-source software, user data is safely encrypted and stored. In the context of AI4EOSC, it is used for example to store auth tokens of external services (Huggingface), connection tokens with internal components (Storage), password of internal components (MLflow), Federated Learning client tokens, etc.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encrypted storage of user sensitive information. • Interfacing through the platform API. • Used for saving tokens and passwords to connect to different platform components and external services.
Code	https://github.com/hashicorp/vault
Technologies	Vault
License	Business Source License 1.1
Endpoints	https://secrets.services.ai4os.eu:8200/

Container Registry

Name	Container Registry
Developed	Externally
Description	The AI4EOSC Container Registry is used to store the different Docker container assets of the platform. For example, we use it to store the container images of the platform components (e.g. Platform Dashboard). We also use it to store (as part of our CI/CD pipeline) the Docker images of the user's AI modules, mirroring them to Docker Hub. Finally, we also use it to allow users to save snapshots of their Dashboard deployment for later redeployments.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage of AI module catalog images. • Storage of platform component's container images. • Storage of user snapshots.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic mirroring to DockerHub. • Support for bot accounts that integrate with the Platform API.
Code	https://github.com/goharbor/harbor
Technologies	Harbor
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://registry.services.ai4os.eu/

Storage

Name	Storage
Developed	Externally
Description	The AI4EOSC Storage is used to store all the user related data. It is seamlessly connected from the Platform Dashboard and WMS component using Rclone, allowing users to access their data from inside their deployments.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage of user datasets and trained models. • Connected with the Dashboard and WMS, allowing users to access data from inside the deployments. • Used to automatically retrieve external datasets during deployment launching. • Used to store automatic backups of the user annotation in the CVAT tool.
Code	https://github.com/nextcloud
Technologies	Nextcloud
License	GNU Affero GPL v3.0
Endpoints	https://share.services.ai4os.eu/

Status

Name	Status monitoring
Developed	Externally

Description	The AI4EOSC Status monitoring is a service to periodically monitor the uptime of the different AI4EOSC components. The service monitors the public endpoints of all components, opening a GitHub issue assigned to the component developer if a downtime is detected.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live monitoring of any endpoint. • Clear UI for visualization. • Automatic issue opening assigned to the appropriate component developer. • Self-hosted in GitHub: Issues as incident reports, Actions as uptime monitors, and Pages for the status page.
Code	https://github.com/AI4EOSC/status https://github.com/uptime/uptime
Technologies	Uptime, GitHub
License	MIT
Endpoints	https://status.ai4eosc.eu/

Dynamic DNS

Name	Dynamics DNS
Developed	Externally
Description	The Dynamic DNS is a service to manage dynamic DNS for the project's components. It is used by component developers to register Hostnames for their services, pointing to the appropriate machine. It is used by every AI4EOSC component that has a public endpoint under the ai4eosc.eu domain.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frontend to perform Dynamic DNS updates via dyndns2 protocol. • Backend using Dynamic DNS UPDATE protocol (RFC 2136) to update compatible nameservers, as well as optionally using the dyndns2 protocol to update other services. • Supports IPv4, IPv6 and TLS. • Manages all the project related Domains (cloud.ai4eosc.eu, dev.ai4eosc.eu, services.ai4os.eu), which gather the Hosts of the different components (e.g. Dashboard, Storage, etc.)
Code	https://github.com/nsupdate-info/nsupdate.info
Technologies	Python, Django
License	BSD

Endpoints	https://nsupdate.fedcloud.eu/
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3.2 - WP4 COMPONENTS

In this section, we present services developed under WP4 (Next Generation AI Platform as a Service):

PaaS Orchestration

Name	PaaS Orchestrator System
Developed	Internally
Description	The PaaS Orchestrator System allows to coordinate the provisioning of virtualized compute and storage resources on Cloud Management Frameworks, both private and public, as well as the deployment of complex services on Kubernetes clusters. It receives the deployment requests, expressed through templates written in TOSCA, and orchestrates the deployments on the best available provider via the Infrastructure Manager (IM). In order to select the best site, the PaaS Orchestrator System implements a complex workflow, based on AI techniques, gathering information about the SLAs signed by the providers with the user, the monitoring data about the availability of the compute and storage services, the location of the data requested by the user.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TOSCA-based deployment orchestration service on multiple IaaS, • Cloud-oriented federation service, • Ready-to-deploy user-oriented services over cloud IaaS and PaaS.
Code	https://github.com/inf-n-datacloud/orchestrator
Technologies	Java, Python, OpenStack, Kubernetes
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it

Infrastructure Manager

Name	Infrastructure Manager
Developed	Internally
Description	Infrastructure Manager is an IaaS tool designed to manage the creation of virtual infrastructures by deploying and configuring virtual machines on different cloud providers, making infrastructures cloud-agnostic. It automates the deployment and management of the virtual infrastructures.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automation of virtualized infrastructure deployment and configuration with software installation. • Support for multiple Cloud back-ends (public, on-premises, federated) and Kubernetes. • Multi-modal access (Web-based application for user-friendly interface, command-line application for advanced usage and REST API for easier integration).
Code	https://github.com/grycap/im
Technologies	Python, TOSCA
License	GNU GPL 3.0
Endpoints	https://im.egi.eu

Workload Management System

Name	Federated WMS
Developed	Externally
Description	The Federated Workload Management System (Federated WMS) enables orchestrated workload execution across multiple datacenters through a WAN-federated architecture. Built using HashiCorp Nomad and Consul, this system allows participating organizations to share and schedule jobs in a distributed, cloud-agnostic manner. It supports high-availability and multi-tenancy by federating multiple clusters. It can be deployed using a series of Ansible recipes.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WAN-federated architecture using HashiCorp Nomad and Consul. • Multi-datacenter workload orchestration.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service discovery and health checking across federated clusters. • Decentralized job scheduling and execution. • Supports interactive and batch jobs. • Easy deployment and management through Ansible recipes.
Code	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-ansible https://github.com/hashicorp/nomad
Technologies	Ansible, Consul, Nomad, Docker
License	Apache 2.0, Business Source License 1.1
Endpoints	Endpoints are not publicly available.

Inference platform

Name	AI as a Service
Developed	Internally
Description	The AI as a Service (AlaaS) is a platform based on OSCAR (Open-source Serverless Computing for Data-Processing Applications) for serverless event-driven data-processing applications that allows the deployment of AI models as services on cloud environments, providing an accessible and efficient means to perform inference.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different methods of deploying services: as serverless functions reacting to events, scalable short-lived endpoints and long-lived exposed services for on-premises deployments. • Automated integration with the AI4EOSC platform, with continuous delivery in place. • Integration with different storage systems (e.g. MinIO, Onedata, dCache). • Multi-tenancy based on EGI Check-In and AI4EOSC AAI with support for multiple Virtual Organizations (VOs).
Code	https://github.com/grycap/oscar
Technologies	Go, Kubernetes, Knative, MinIO
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/

3.3 - WP5 COMPONENTS

In this section we present services developed under WP5 (Composite AI and experiment centric services):

Platform API

Name	Platform API
Developed	Internally
Description	The AI4EOSC Platform API seamlessly orchestrates the different platform components. Through a unified interface it provides endpoints to interact with the different platform components including the AI catalog, the Workload Management System, the AlaaS, the Storage, and many more.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endpoints to list all available AI modules and tools (federated learning, CVAT, LLMs). • Endpoints to retrieve metadata from AI modules and tools, with option to convert among profiles and formats. • Endpoints to retrieve the configuration to deploy all AI modules and tools. • Endpoints to deploy all AI modules and tools in the WMS, in either try-mode, standard mode or batch mode. • Endpoints to snapshot WMS deployments into the AI4OS Container registry. • Endpoints to deploy AI modules in the AI4OS Inference Platform. • Endpoints to interact with the AI4OS Storage. • Endpoints to interact with the AI4OS Secrets management. • Endpoints to interact with the AI4OS LLM. • Endpoints to interact with Zenodo via a proxy. • Endpoints to retrieve stats from the WMS. • Supports authentication to protected endpoints.
Code	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-papi
Technologies	Python, FastAPI
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/

Platform Dashboard

Name	Platform Dashboard
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Developed	Internally
Description	The AI4EOSC Platform Dashboard provides an easy-to-use interface to develop artificial intelligence and machine learning models in the EOSC. It also allows users to deploy and interact with their own LLM instances. It uses the Platform API to connect with all the platform components.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive catalog of AI modules and tools. • Rich metadata for module lineage and provenance. • Interactive development environments. • Transparent access to the federated model training resources. • Execution of persistent and batch deployments. • Straightforward inference deployments to the AlaaS platform. • Integrations to deploy in the EOSC Node and external cloud providers. • Automated dataset synchronisation. • Account synchronisation with the AI4EOSC Storage and external storage providers. • Account synchronisation with Hugging Face to access and use LLM models. • Statistics about user and overall usage of the platform.
Code	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-dashboard
Technologies	Angular (Typescript, CSS, HTML)
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production instance: https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/ • Plausible analytics service: https://stats.services.ai4os.eu/ • Customized version for the AI4Life project: https://ai4life.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/ • Customized version for the iMagine project: https://dashboard.cloud.imagine-ai.eu/

Provenance manager

Name	Provenance Manager
Developed	Internally
Description	The AI4EOSC Provenance Manager is a tool responsible for fetching metadata from the different AI4EOSC components and building a detailed provenance graph of the applications published in the AI4EOSC marketplace. The resulting provenance graph can be visualized in an interactive way in the AI4EOSC dashboard. Moreover, a LLM-based querying service has been deployed to query the graph using natural language. The provenance information is automatically generated for all

	the applications included in the marketplace and is exposed using different metadata schemas.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Semantic provenance information, parsing from the information from several AI4EOSC components (Platform API, Experiment Registry, CI/CD pipeline). • Interactive visualization. • LLM-based interaction. • Crosswalks for different metadata schemas.
Code	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-provenance
Technologies	Resource Description Framework (RDF), RDF Mapping language (RML), PROV Ontology (PROV-O), Spring Framework, PostgreSQL, React, D3js, Large Language Models (LLMs), Model Context Protocol (MCP).
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://provenance.services.ai4os.eu/

AI4Compose

Name	AI4Compose
Developed	Internally
Description	AI4Compose is a software suite designed to integrate and orchestrate various AI models and machine learning techniques into organised workflows. It supports the visual programming tools Elyra and Node-RED, allowing users to create and manage AI inference pipelines through intuitive graphical interfaces. AI4Compose is integrated with OSCAR for executing inference tasks, facilitating the incorporation of AI models into data science workflows with precision and efficiency.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual composition of AI inference pipelines. • User-friendly interface with a drag-and-drop approach. • Integration with OSCAR to efficiently outsource AI model inference on distributed infrastructures. • Integration with EGI Notebooks. • Custom nodes to use the models of the AI4EOSC Marketplace.
Code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GitHub: https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-compose • AI4Compose collection in Node-RED Library: https://flows.nodered.org/collection/4pW6ET9DMHs0
Technologies	Flowfuse, Node-RED, Jupyter Notebooks, Elyra, OSCAR
License	Apache 2.0

Endpoints	Node-RED (FlowFuse): https://forge.flows.dev.ai4eosc.eu Elyra (integrated in EGI Notebooks): https://notebooks.egi.eu Node collection: https://flows.nodered.org/collection/4pW6ET9DMHs0
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Experiment tracking and Model Registry

Name	Experiment tracking and Model Registry
Developed	Externally (with some internally developed components)
Description	The AI4EOSC Experiment tracking and Model Registry is used to log the information of the AI module training, as well as saving the final models. We have also developed a web application that provides a GUI to the MLflow Authentication API for self-registration.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central place for users to store AI/ML experiments, runs, and models. • Self-registration AAI using OIDC. • User-friendly handling of experiment and model permissions. • Automatic backup and manual restore. • User credentials are stored in the Secrets Manager service via the AI4OS Platform API.
Code	https://github.com/mlflow/mlflow https://github.com/m-team-kit/mlflow-auth-gui
Technologies	MLflow, PostgreSQL, Sqlite, Flask, React, Traefik
License	MIT
Endpoints	https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/

Drift detection

Name	Frouros
Developed	Internally
Description	Fouros is a Python library to detect both concept drift and data drift in data. It has been developed to support a wide array of detectors from different families. It works along the DriftWatch service to provide users with reliable monitoring of their production models.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports concept drift and data drift. • Supports streaming and batch methods.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support 32 different detectors, grouped into families. • Framework agnostic: supports Sklearn, Tensorflow, Pytorch, etc. • Support for tabular data and images.
Code	https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/frouros
Technologies	Python, Numpy, Scipy
License	BSD 3
Endpoints	Local installation

Drift monitoring

Name	DriftWatch
Developed	Internally
Description	DriftWatch allows to visualize drift detection in deployed AI models. Using a Python client, it is able to send the drift metrics generated by any drift detection framework (e.g. Frouros) to a central server, where it can be visualized in a friendly and intuitive interface.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central place for users to store drift analysis results. • OIDC AAI. • User-friendly frontend for drift monitoring. • OpenAPI v3 documented backend with Swagger interface. • Agnostic to the drift detection framework (works with Frouros, Alibi-detect, Evidently, etc.). • Python client for script integration.
Code	https://github.com/m-team-kit/drift-watch
Technologies	MongoDB, Flask, React and Docker
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://drift-watch.cloud.ai4eosc.eu

Metadata manager

Name	Metadata manager
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Developed	Internally
Description	The AI4EOSC Metadata Manager is a tool to manage common operations performed on AI4EOSC assets (module and tools) metadata. It allows for migration, validation, versioning and mapping between profiles.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata validation, both in JSON and YAML syntax. • Metadata migration between versions. • Metadata mapping between different profiles (e.g. MLDCAT-AP) and formats (e.g. JSON-LD, Turtle).
Code	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-metadata/
Technologies	Python, JSON schema
License	Apache 2.0
Endpoints	Local installation

CI/CD

Name	CI/CD pipeline manager
Developed	Externally
Description	The AI4EOSC CI/CD pipeline manager is a service to orchestrate the CI/CD Pipelines of the different AI modules and tools. It implements an extensive set of checks to ensure the quality of the AI modules that are included in the AI4EOSC Marketplace.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A robust well-designed pipeline, common for all modules, designed via tox. • Automatic trigger when code changes are pushed. • Support for code style analysis via flake8. • Support for unit testing via pytest. • Support for security scanners via bandit. • Support for metadata validation with AI4OS Metadata manager. • Support for Docker images building into the AI4OS Container Registry. • Basic testing of the built AI modules, that they properly start DEEPaaS API • Support for updates to the different AI4OS components (Inference Platform, Platform API). • automatic archiving to Zenodo if needed. • Automatic triggers to the provenance component.

Code	https://github.com/jenkinsci/jenkins https://github.com/ai4os/ai4os-hub-ga
Technologies	Jenkins, tox, flake8, pytest, bandit
License	MIT
Endpoints	https://jenkins.services.ai4os.eu/

AI4EOSC LLM

Name	AI4EOSC LLM
Developed	Externally
Description	The AI4EOSC LLM allows users to interact with a catalog of deployed Large Language Models, including both text-based and vision based models from several open-source AI providers (Mistral, Qwen). Through protected OpenAI-compatible APIs, users are able to integrate this service into their own components.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Friendly UI to interact with LLM. • Catalog of different open-source LLMs. • Supports both text-based and vision-based workloads. • Open-AI compatible API to integrate with external services.
Code	https://github.com/vllm-project/vllm https://github.com/open-webui/open-webui
Technologies	vLLM, Open WebUI
License	Apache 2.0, OpenWebUI custom license
Endpoints	https://llm.dev.ai4eosc.eu/

3.4 - WP6 COMPONENTS

Finally, services whose development work has been performed by WP6, AI applications and tools, are presented in this section.

Templates Hub

Name	Templates Hub
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Developed	Internally
Description	The AI4 Templates Hub allows developers and users to create software project repositories, following AI4EOSC best practices and recommendations. These templates provide an easier path to integrate a module in the AI4EOSC marketplace, as they include all the required metadata and other code assets needed. It features a user-friendly web interface to generate new repositories.
Key features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different template flavours, focusing on different user needs (advanced, minimal, child-module). • Easier integration of user developed modules in the AI4OS marketplace. • Web interface and API for effortless generation of software projects.
Code	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-template https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-template-adv https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-template-child https://github.com/m-team-kit/cookiecutter-web https://github.com/m-team-kit/cookiecutter-web-backend
Technologies	Cookiecutter, Next JS, Python, PostgreSQL, FastAPI
License	MIT, Apache 2.0
Endpoints	https://templates.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/

4. EOSC INTEGRATION

AI4EOSC has made a continuous effort to contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. In addition to the participation in the horizontal activities carried out in the EOSC FOCUS HE discussion groups and related organized events, such as the EOSC Winter School or the EOSC Symposium (presented in more detail in Deliverable 2.4 [D2.4]), in this section we present the work done integrating the AI4EOSC AI models with the EOSC EU Node. Moreover, we share our plans to register the AI4EOSC services in the EOSC Service Catalogue.

4.1 - EOSC EU NODE

The EOSC EU Node [eu-node] serves as the digital portal to the EOSC initiative. Its primary goal is to enable seamless access to research data, services, and tools across Europe. It supports the sharing of resources, collaborative work through interactive notebooks, and the use of virtual machines and containers, promoting open science and enhanced collaboration among researchers.

Among the multiple options that AI4EOSC offers to deploy AI models in production, the project has made an effort to allow model deployment directly in the EOSC EU Node resources. For this scenario, two deployment options are currently supported:

- **Deploying in a container** (OKD-based): This option provides fast deployment times, but it doesn't provide access to the execution environment. This is made available via the "AI4EOSC Module Container" tool in the Tools Hub [\[toolshub-container\]](#).
- **Deploying in a virtual machine** (OpenStack-based): When deploying using a virtual machine, the deployment time required is longer compared with containers, but it allows full access to the execution environment. This is made available via the "AI4EOSC Module VM" tool in the Tools Hub [\[toolshub-vm\]](#).

In this way, European researchers are provided with flexible options to deploy the AI models developed by AI4EOSC, supported by the free computing credits available through the EOSC EU Node. We presented this integration work in the past EOSC Winter School 2025, and published a piece of news to the website and social media. More information can be found in the AI4OS documentation and in the video tutorial on the AI4EOSC youtube channel [\[docs-eu-node\]](#).

Moreover, we have also integrated, in the context of WP4, resources coming from the EOSC EU Node in the AI4EOSC Nomad Cluster [\[wp4-eu-node\]](#). Thus, the federated development cluster of AI4EOSC has been extended using EU node resources based on virtual machines. Specifically, we have integrated a new Nomad server together with three Nomad clients with 8 CPUs and 32 GBs of RAM in total. More details are provided in Deliverable D4.4 [\[D4.4\]](#).

4.2 - EOSC SERVICE CATALOGUE

AI4EOSC has promoted the sharing and reuse of scientific assets, and because of that, our intention from the beginning of the project was to foster cross-disciplinary collaboration by integrating our catalogue and marketplace into the old EOSC portal.

An initial onboarding of resources was performed in the legacy EOSC marketplace services, making it possible to browse the services in the EOSC Portal and Marketplace (from EOSC-Future) and in the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub. However, all services onboarded in the former EOSC Marketplace were removed from the current Resource Hub of the EOSC EU Node. Service onboarding to the EOSC Federation will be re-enabled in the near future across all available Nodes.

The portal is being replaced by a new implementation carried out by the EOSC Beyond project [\[eosc-beyond\]](#). Currently, the catalogue is at pre-production stage, where partners from the Pilots of the project are registering themselves as providers, listing their services and merging other catalogues as well as helping validate the current implementation.

Once the new catalogue opens to external contributors, the AI4EOSC project is committed to register the AI4EOSC services. We will analyze, together with the responsables of the EOSC Service Catalogue, the best approach to onboard the

services, such as registering the AI4EOSC platform as a service, or allowing to discover the AI4EOSC marketplace models in the Discovery Hub.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has presented the final version of the catalogue of services of the AI4EOSC platform, composed of 9 different services. These services have been broken into service components, thematically organized into work packages. Finally we have described our successful efforts in integrating with the EOSC ecosystem, both by allowing deploying our AI modules into the EOSC EU node, as well as by integrating the EOSC EU Node resources into our federated Workload Management System. Finally we remain committed to offer our services in the EOSC Service Catalogue based on the outcomes of the EOSC Beyond project.

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